

Leveraging Data to Set Objectives and Make Decision: What Can We Learn from Impact Assessments?
The Experience from IFAD
For Data for Policy 2022 Conference

Abstract

Motivation

Rural development program formulation and project design need solid evidence, especially from rigorous impact assessments of previous projects. Among multilateral development institutions, measuring results achieved at the project and corporate level is of utmost importance to maximize the effectiveness of the funds invested and to ensure their value for money.

Impact assessment is an approach to measure outcomes and impacts achieved by development projects and to understand the specific mechanisms that led to the attributable impacts. IFAD is committed to ensuring objective and evidence-based assessment and reporting of results, with associated documentation of lessons and good practices learned from IFAD-supported projects that target remote regions of developing countries and fragile situations. IFAD's impact assessment not only assesses the impact of individual projects but also of the institution as a whole. In addition, IFAD supports key actors use survey data in more and better ways in partner countries to inform rural development policies through the [50X2030 initiative](#).¹

Objectives

The main goal of the panel session is to discuss the policy relevant findings from rigorous impact assessments as well as the lessons learned and how these can feed into future project design and implementation and policymaking. The event will thus discuss whether and how quantitative findings from impact assessments are used to inform the design of country strategies and the development of new programs and projects.

The panel session will provide: (1) an overview of theory and practices of using impact evaluation to measure results and inform new projects, programs and targets, drawing from recent impact assessments of IFAD supported projects; and (2) insights on how to spur effective use of lessons learned and results to make decisions.

Outline/Style

The panel session will start with a presentation on the approach taken to conduct rigorous impact assessments and to aggregate and project impacts achieved at corporate level on IFAD operations. The main takeaways from this effort will also be discussed. This will be followed by three short

¹ The 50x2030 initiative is a 10-year, approximately US\$500 million initiative that aims to increase the capacity of 50 low and lower middle-income countries to produce, analyse, interpret, and apply data to decisions in the agricultural sector that support rural development and food security. It is Implemented through a unique partnership between the World Bank, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD).

presentations that summarize policy relevant findings from impact assessments of IFAD-supported projects. The topics covered are particularly important for the livelihoods of small-scale producers and include value chain interventions, women’s empowerment in rural areas, and climate change adaptation for sustainable rural transformations. A Q&A session will enrich the dialogue and make sure actionable solutions are adequately addressed.

PRESENTATION 1: “Going from Project to Corporate Level Impact Assessments. IFAD’s Experience”
By Sara Savastano and Aslihan Arslan

Abstract

Conducting systematic impact assessments is a key step in the process of enhancing development effectiveness. At the corporate level, they help measure progress and achievements as well as inform the setting of new and more ambitious targets for the future. At the project level, they document successes and areas of improvement for each project, as well as the mechanisms through which impacts are achieved.

IFAD is the only international financial institution with such a systematic approach to corporate reporting using rigorous impact assessments. IFAD conducts impact assessments on at least 15 per cent of its project portfolio. The projects are selected for impact assessments in an attempt to be representative of IFAD's overall interventions. This allows IFAD to report on the corporate impacts of its operations making.

Findings of impact assessments are also used to learn lessons that inform decision-making. The impact assessments are designed in close collaboration with local stakeholders and government counterparts to ensure relevant lessons are learned. As part of the impact assessments, IFAD collects both quantitative and qualitative data to draw out richer lessons.

The first step of IFAD’s methodology to estimate aggregate development effectiveness involves a meta-analysis of individual project impact estimates to compute aggregate corporate impacts.² Next, a projection exercise is conducted to extrapolate the mean impact estimates from the meta-analysis to the rest of IFAD portfolio and estimate the number of people benefiting from IFAD interventions.

This presentation will summarize the methodology used to go from project to corporate level impacts of IFAD operations in relation to its mandate of reaching the poorest in rural areas of developing countries. It will also present the corporate level impacts of IFAD’s operations between 2019 and 2021 on the livelihoods of the rural poor and the major lessons learned from this exercise.

² Meta-analysis is a statistical procedure for combining data from multiple studies, or in the specific case of IFAD, project impact estimates. Meta-analysis can be defined as results synthesis or “the statistical analysis of a large collection of results for the purpose of integrating the findings” (Glass 1976). In other words, it is “a quantitative summary of statistical indicators reported in similar empirical studies” (Brander et al. 2006).

PRESENTATION 2: “Investing in Value Chain for Rural Transformation”

By Athur Mabiso, Tisorn Songsermsawas

Abstract

Agriculture is the main source of income for 70 per cent of poor rural households in developing countries. Although small-scale producers have the highest share of production, they continue to account for the lowest share of market value and are often in a weaker bargaining position vis-à-vis other value chain (VC) actors such as traders, off-takers, and aggregators. VCs are integral to rural transformation. As rural economies and food systems transform, agricultural productivity increases to meet increasing urban food demand, while VCs become longer and more complex. This process is accompanied by an increase in the small-medium enterprises in the midstream of the value chain (processing, packaging, transportation, and distribution) which can promote the inclusion of small-scale producers with the right investments.

Pro-poor VC interventions have the potential to improve livelihoods sustainably and promote inclusiveness and empowerment. As a result, for more than 20 years, IFAD has invested substantially in the design and implementation of pro-poor VC development projects. Between 2007 and 2018, out of the total US\$10.2 billion approved by IFAD in various projects, 68 per cent (US\$6.96 billion) was for value-chain-relevant projects. This share has increased to 80 per cent in the last 3 years (IOE IFAD, 2019).

This presentation will summarise lessons learned from six IFAD-supported projects with a VC component that have undergone a rigorous ex-post impact assessment, with a specific focus on identifying practical solutions to address constraints to sustainable and inclusive rural development. The projects cover the following countries: Mozambique, Nicaragua, Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands, the United Republic of Tanzania and Zambia. Results show that value chain development interventions can have far-reaching impacts on agricultural market access and production, with occasional impacts income and food security and in some cases also empowering women and improving nutrition (dietary diversity). However, where constraints are not adequately addressed by VC interventions, which often would require complementary access to production inputs, information, and technology, development impacts can also be quite limited. Therefore, understanding the limiting factors in value chains offer insights to better design interventions for value chain development.

PRESENTATION 3: IMPACTS OF IFAD PROJECTS ON MULTIPLE DIMENSIONS OF WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT

Carlo Azzarri¹, Beliyou Haile¹, Sedi-Anne Boukaka¹, Greg Seymour¹, Jessica Heckert¹, Ruth Meinzen-Dick¹, Agnes Quisumbing¹, Alessandra Garbero², Athur Mabiso², Aslihan Arslan², Romina Cavatassi², Tisorn Songsermsawas², Sara Savastano², Adriana Paolantonio³, Rawane Yasser⁴, Chloe van Biljon⁵, Neha Paliwal⁶, Irene Toma⁷, Gianluca Franceschini⁷

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Abstract

Rural transformation is an integral component of economic development, which leads to reduction in poverty and improvement in women's empowerment. Complete equality between men and women, however, cannot be reached without specific policy action (Duflo, 2012). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have added renewed emphasis on women's empowerment in the development discourse as 11 of the 17 SDGs require improvements in indicators related to gender dynamics, even though the SDG5 is the only one directly addressing gender inequality (Doss et al. 2018).

Promoting gender equality and women's empowerment in rural areas is one of the key objectives of IFAD. It comprises three dimensions: economic empowerment to enable both rural women and men to participate in and benefit from profitable economic activities (economic empowerment); equal voice of men and women to influence rural institutions and organizations, including decision making processes at the household, community, and local level (voice and decision-making); and a more equitable balance in workload and in sharing economic and social benefits between women and men (equitable workloads).

Our paper contributes to the understanding of the impacts of IFAD investments on gender equity and women's empowerment, focusing on a synthesis of existing evidence on the types of welfare-improving interventions. More specifically, we summarize findings from six impact assessments of IFAD supported projects that have used the integrated Women's Empowerment in Agriculture Index (i-WEAI) to estimate impacts on multiple dimensions of women's empowerment.³ Focusing on this

³The Women's Empowerment in Agriculture Index (WEAI) (Alkire et al., 2013) and the project-level WEAI (pro-WEAI), the newest version of WEAI designed as a diagnostic and impact assessment tool for agricultural development projects (Malapit et al., 2019), measure inclusion and empowerment of both sexes in the agricultural sector. The integrated-WEAI (i-WEAI), is a novel approach to measure women's empowerment that is intended to prevent duplication of survey questions (via minor modifications of pro-WEAI data collection methodology) and reduce overall survey time.

methodology and using data disaggregated by sex, we present the results of the IAs of the six IFAD programs conducted in three different IFAD regions and focusing on a variety of activities and sectors, including agriculture value chains (Mali-PMR, Nigeria-VCDP, and Tanzania-MIVARF), household business enterprises (Ghana-REP III) and natural resources management (Kenya-UTaNRMP and Djibouti-PRAREV). Although all programs paid a particular attention to vulnerable groups and especially women, the evidence suggests large variations in their impacts on gender-related indicators. Overall, while many programs worked towards encouraging joint decision making on income generating activities, they sometimes fell short on improving actual female participation. Finally, female asset ownership is a dimension for which progress is still very much needed overall, as lack of impacts or poor performances were observed for most programs. Particular attention should be devoted to women land ownership, tenure, and property rights that have remained unimproved in all cases. This study also identifies guiding principles for project/program design and policymaking that improve women's empowerment.

PRESENTATION 4: Investing towards Environmentally Sustainable Livestock Development

By Sinafikeh Gemessa and Romina Cavatassi

Abstract

Livestock contribute to about 40% of agricultural GDP at global level and are an essential source of livelihood for hundreds of millions of poor people and are critical to human health, global food and nutritional security.

Yet the livestock sector production is affected by climate change while also contributing to the problem. Droughts directly affect livestock health and productivity while also reducing forage. Pastures also get highly degraded with intensive grazing. These have severe consequences for the rural poor that depend on the livestock sector. The sector also contributes to climate change with some 14.5% of total anthropogenic greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions at global level coming from livestock production and processing.

However, carbon neutral livestock production is possible and IFAD has been already funding, experiencing and measuring interventions aimed at pasture restoration and increased livestock productivity while reducing ecological footprint.

There are a number of strategies to achieve adaptation and pasture restoration while increasing productivity. These strategies are geared towards reduced emissions but also towards adaptation to climatic changes. They include, among others: improved feeding efficiency, circular systems, rotational pasture combined with improved feeding and sequestering carbon in the soils. Context tailored livestock practices have the potential to reduce GHG emissions while improving productivity, adaptation and resilience at the same time, objectives which can be measured with rigorous methods through impact assessments.

The event will present challenges and opportunities, impacts and achievements, due to climate change for the livestock sector and for people that derive their livelihood from it. The session will present specific examples from Tajikistan where IFAD supported poor small-scale livestock farmers, private veterinary service providers, and vulnerable women-headed households by establishing and strengthening farmers' organizations, increasing livestock productivity through livestock and veterinary services and fodder supply, and increasing their access to more productive and climate resilient pastures and livelihood diversification activities.